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Evaluation of Online Reviews on Tripadvisor for 5-Star Accommodation Businesses during the Covid-19: The Case of Bodrum

Abstract

With the development of technology, the interest in internet usage has increased. This situation significantly affects the purchasing behavior of consumers. Consumers in purchasing behavior share their experiences using Web 2.0 tools and provide insights for other consumers. In the light of this information, consumers realize their purchasing decision-making processes. There are many social networking platforms where consumers share their reviews online. One of these platforms is the Tripadvisor website. The aim of this study was to examine the changes in the purchasing behavior of consumers during the pandemic period. By the help of content analysis, 4649 comments of the visitors attained who had accommodation experience in 405-star accommodation establishments operating in Bodrum. The study consists of comments from users on the Tripadvisor website. According to the findings, it was determined that the customers made the most positive comments in the personnel category, and the most negative comments were made in the food and beverage category. In this study, suggestions were made for tourism marketers and business managers.

Keywords: *Covid-19, Hotel, Hospitality, Online Consumer Reviews, e-WOM, Tripadvisor*

JEL Classifications: L83; M30; M31

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1.Introduction

Today, with the advancement of technology, the use of the internet has increased. Although the dictionary meaning of the internet is expressed as "network between networks", it can be defined as a large "computer network" that allows many computers to be connected to each other (Özdipçiner, 2010: 7). In the historical process, the development of the Internet started

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with Web 1.0 at the beginning of the 1990s, and while people were in a passive position, they became active with Web 2.0 in the 2000s (Kapan and Üncel, 2020: 277). Web 2.0 definition is “A collection of open source, interactive and user-controlled online applications that increase users' experience, knowledge and market power as participants in business and social processes” (Constantinides and Fountain, 2008: 232). In this case, users started to interact with other users by producing their own content thanks to Web 2.0 technology.

According to the “Digital in 2021” report prepared in cooperation with WeAreSocial and Hootsuite, %77,7 of the population is internet users as of January, while %70,8 of the population appears to be active social media users. It is seen that there are active social media users (Kemp, 2021). Research shows that the internet users are constantly increasing. Because, thanks to websites, people share visual and audio documents and also affect other users with comments containing their experiences (Çuhadar et al., 2018: 228).

The concept of “Electronic Word of Mouth (e-WOM)” emerges at the point where users interact with each other online and share their experiences with large audiences. (Cheung and Thadani, 2010). By using online applications such as blogs, comment sites, forums, newsgroups, and social networks, the effects of traditional word-of-mouth communication have decreased and electronic word-of-mouth communication has emerged (See-To and Ho, 2014). It has been revealed in many studies that the Internet has become one of the most important sources, especially in travel and travel decision-making (Ateş and Boz, 2015: 65). It has become one of the most effective tools utilized (Giritlioğlu et al., 2016: 206).

The wishes of people and the experiences they desire to live can be affected by many situations globally. Especially with the current Covid-19 pandemic, people's preferences and priorities have changed. The Covid-19 pandemic, which emerged on December 31, 2019 (T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı Covid-19 Rehberi, 2020) in the city of Wuhan, Hubei Province of the People's Republic of China, caused changes all over the world and many measures were taken. There has been a decrease in the expenditures of the people who prefer to travel (Aylan, 2020: 165) and it has been revealed that individuals who prefer to travel prefer less well-known and quiet places compared to crowded destinations (Yaşar, 2020). It is known that factors such as safety and security are important (Reisinger and Mavondo, 2005). In this case, it is necessary to take various measures for such epidemics in businesses and destinations. In particular, while tourism enterprises should give more importance to health, hygiene and safety measures compared to the period before the pandemic, it is normal for customers' expectations to change (Aydın and Doğan, 2020: 102).

Against this backdrop, the current study aimed to examine the visitors' comments on the Tripadvisor website from 5-star hotel accommodation establishments operating in the Bodrum District of Muğla Province. For this study, especially the pandemic period was chosen and it was carried out to examine the purchasing behaviors of the customers and the service quality determinants that are very important for tourism marketing and tourism sector managers. In the following section, the customer satisfaction related to electronic word-of-mouth communication, the comments on Tripadvisor, the method, findings, results and suggestions of the study were discussed.

2.Literature Review

2.1 Electronic Word of Mouth Communication (e-WOM)

In the times when the internet was not widespread, traditional word of mouth marketing was realized when people shared their comments about the product or service they experienced in the environment of friends or family (Okan and Şahin, 2016). With the spread of the Internet, people have started to communicate from the virtual environment instead of the natural environment, and social media and forums are becoming the channels where information is exchanged most intensively (Özaslan, 2014: 73). Thanks to Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), the era of traditional word-of-mouth communication has ended and

electronic word-of-mouth communication has emerged (Lin, 2009). Electronic word-of-mouth communication is the sharing of positive or negative experiences of existing or potential customers via the internet (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004: 39).

Customers can report their opinions and experiences on blogs, discussion forums, websites, newsgroups and social media sharing sites (Cheung and Thadani, 2010: 330). (Genç, 2014: 1037). According to the study of Akar (2009: 115), the level of interaction between consumers in choosing different brands has been found to be more effective than newspapers and magazines, personal selling and radio advertisements.

As the comments shared by the consumers do not carry a commercial concern, they become a more reliable and credible source of information, and the first source that consumers refer to in their search for information has been customer comments (Taşkıran, 2020: 748). In their study, Ergenekon and Güven (2018) collected data from 329 academic staff who bought vacations from the internet. According to the research findings, it was determined that factors such as electronic word of mouth communication, trust and image have a significant and positive relationship on online purchasing behavior.

Bozbay et al. (2017) collected data from 335 social media users through a survey. According to the findings, it was determined that there is a significant relationship between electronic loyalty, trust and electronic word of mouth communication. In many studies in the literature, it is seen that potential customers take reference from the comments of existing customers in decision-making (Bilim et al., 2013). Electronic word of mouth communication is shown as an important resource for consumers to reach personal comments about products or services, especially for experiences such as tourism and accommodation sector (Lee et al., 2008).

The fact that tourism services are intangible and inexperienced beforehand, the risk perception for consumers and the lack of personal communication areas lead to interpretations as an e-information source (Göral, 2015: 2).

A lot of research has been carried out in the literature on online comments on various websites. In Yavuz's (2020)'s study, comments about 4 and 5 star hotels in Ordu province were analyzed on the Trivago website. It has been determined that the guests are satisfied with the location and view of the hotels, but they are not satisfied with the food and beverage service of the hotels, especially the breakfast service. In the study of Muradi and Akbıyık (2020), online comments from 5 different cultures of a hotel in Antalya were analyzed. According to the findings, services that cause positive and negative cultural comments include cleaning, shuttle bus, room service and pool for Germans, mini club, ice cream and animation for Russians, restaurant, water park, shuttle bus and Turkish bath for Turks. There is the comfort of having a holiday with children, a snack restaurant, evening entertainment and an animation team, while for Dutch Tourists there is a friendly staff, a pool, a la carte restaurant and a variety of food. In addition, Doğan (2017)'s study analyzed the comments and ratings made on the Booking.com website for 2-3-4 and 5-star hotels operating in Aksaray. As a result of the findings, it was determined that the most positive comments were in the category of cleanliness, and the most negative comments were "room facilities and (noise) comfort". In the study of Akgöz and Tengilimoğlu (2015), which was made on the same website, Booking.com, it was examined whether there was a difference in satisfaction scores in line with the characteristics of 302 Antalya hotels with 3, 4 and 5 stars. It has been revealed that the satisfaction of the businesses with more stars is higher than the hotels with less number of stars. The location criterion that the customers were most satisfied with was determined as the wifi quality, and the criterion they were least satisfied with. Examining whether there is a significance between online customer scores and the type of accommodation businesses, Çuhadar et al. (2018), on the other hand, hypotheses were formed to determine the differences between online customer scores and location, price range, type of business and legal status. The online comments made to 30 accommodation businesses,

consisting of 21 hotels and 9 hostels operating in the province of Isparta, were analyzed. According to the findings, there was a significant difference between the online customer scores and the type of accommodation establishments. However, it was found that there was no significant difference between the online evaluation scores of the customers and the overnight prices, location and legal status of the enterprises.

The comments made by the consumers are not only important for the customers to share their experiences with each other. It also becomes an important source of information for companies, and becomes a reference for improving service quality and developing marketing strategies.

2.2. Customer Satisfaction and Complaints in Reviews on Tripadvisor

It is increasing day by day that customers transfer their satisfaction and negative situations to online comments. Considering the benefits these comments provide to customers and businesses, it can be said that online comment sites are of great importance. The number of comment sites (Tripadvisor.com, Expedia.com, Booking.com etc.) especially for accommodation businesses is increasing (Yıldız and Çizel, 2016: 35). For example, the Booking.com website offers more than 28 million accommodations in 43 languages (Booking, 2021). Another online comment site Trivago.com, compares the prices of 5 million hotels in more than 190 countries on more than 300 booking sites for users. Tripadvisor is one of the websites with the largest audience among online comment sites.

Tripadvisor, one of the world's largest travel platforms, guides 463 million travelers every month (Tripadvisor, 2021). Tripadvisor, a world-renowned social network in various languages and different versions, provides its users with easy access to many information from hotels to restaurants, from cheap flights to popular destinations (Balıkoğlu et al., 2020: 388). The Tripadvisor website, which has significant effects on businesses or destinations, contains positive and negative customer comments (Banerjee and Chua, 2016). Many studies have been found in the literature on the analysis of online comments made on the Tripadvisor website. Kho et al. (2017) examined 2000 reviews on the Tripadvisor website. As a result of the findings, it has been concluded that websites such as Tripadvisor are very important in the selection of consumers. In addition, Doğancılı et al. (2019) examined customer reviews on the Tripadvisor website of 76 hotel businesses in the Lake District. Provinces such as Konya, Afyonkarahisar, Burdur and Isparta were analyzed in a separate category, under positive and negative categories. It has been determined that the most expressed positive and negative comments are elements such as personnel, cleaning and food. In addition, it has been determined that languages such as Turkish, English, Italian and Chinese are used in consumer comments, respectively. In a similar study by Arkadaş and Ayyıldız (2020), online comments made to 4 and 5 star accommodation businesses in Uludağ were examined. Only negative comments were taken into consideration in the study. Demographic characteristics were evaluated under a separate category; Criteria such as rooms, atmosphere, food and beverage, staff, service, hotel facilities, price and management were added. It was determined that the majority of the comments made were related to the behavior of the personnel. Şahin et al. (2020) analyzed the comments on the Tripadvisor website about 5-star hotels in Kuşadası. Findings obtained from the comments examined in two categories as positive and negative, it was determined that the most complained theme was food and beverage, and the customers tended to make the most comments about staff and food. In addition, in a study by Türkoğlu and Demir (2020), visitor reviews of regions opened to tourism in Malatya province were examined on TripAdvisor.com website. A total of 767 comments in different languages were analyzed and it was determined that the visitors mostly made positive comments about the transportation possibilities to the touristic areas of Malatya. In addition, it has been revealed that the promotion of Malatya province is insufficient.

Some of the studies in the literature are also about how much online comments are given by businesses. Mate et al., (2019) examined what kind of strategy hotel managers follow against comments containing complaints on Tripadvisor. It was concluded that managers consider two dimensions, value and culture, and that hotels are aware of the advantages that can be gained by using appropriate responses. In a study by Ak and Kızıllırmak (2019), it is aimed to evaluate 5-star accommodation businesses operating in Istanbul Beyoğlu in terms of online complaints and online complaint management. By examining 90 negative comments out of a total of 510 online complaints made to 9 5-star accommodation businesses with tourism operation certificate on Tripadvisor, it was found that the most complaints were in the personnel and room categories. 90% of the complaints were returned by the accommodation establishments and it was determined that the majority of the comments were made by the guest relations department manager or the general manager.

3.Methodology

As a result of the literature review, studies with online customer reviews for accommodation establishments in different destinations in Turkey have been found, but no study has been found on online reviews for 5-star accommodation establishments in Bodrum. In similar studies, it was also observed that the pandemic period was not addressed. This study was prepared based on the deficiencies in the literature and was examined with 4649 positive and negative comments by using content analysis method based on the some service quality determinants (pandemic precautions, room, price, staff, cleaning, animation, location, services, food and drink, sea/beach, customer profile, activities for kids, spa/wellness, security, atmosphere, facilities, sports fields and playgrounds) in forty 5-star accommodation businesses that continue their activities during the pandemic period in Bodrum, a district of Muğla province. The comments were compiled between 11.03.2020 and 24.05.2021. In content analysis, according to Kozak (2018: 125), "it is tried to reach a conclusion by looking at the content of written texts, images or discourses, by looking at which concepts, events or thoughts are emphasized most or least." Within the scope of this research, the comments on the website www.tripadvisor.com were examined.

This research is a qualitative research. Data was collected through reviews on the Tripadvisor.com website. The sub-headings of the categories were created by determining the most repetitive words. Then, the percentages of the data were calculated and interpreted.

3.3 Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 includes the genders of users who comment online. The gender of the people who comment on the Tripadvisor website is important to reveal the group with the most reviews. Some users could not identify their gender because they used pseudonyms.

Table 1. Gender Representation.

Gender	N	%
Women	1832	39,40
Man	2353	50,60
unspecified	464	10,00
Total	4649	100,00

Among the people included in the research, it is seen that male customers made the most comments with %50.60, and the lowest comments were made by female customers with %39.40. In Chart 1, the categorical distribution of positive comments made to Bodrum 5-star

accommodation establishments is given. The distributions given in Chart 1 are determined for the services of the enterprises and show which category has the most positive comments.

Chart 1. Categorical Distribution of Positive Comments on Bodrum 5 Star Accommodation Businesses.

Chart 1 shows the categories most mentioned in positive comments. It is seen that the category with the most positive comments is “Personnel”. In Chart 2, the categorical distribution of negative comments made to Bodrum 5-star accommodation establishments is given. Chart 2 reveals the category with the most negative comments.

Chart 2. Categorical Distribution of Negative Comments Made on Bodrum 5 Star Accommodation Business.

Chart 2 shows the categories most frequently mentioned in negative comments. It is seen that the category with the most negative comments is in the "Food and Beverage" category. Online comments include many sub-categories.

The expressions given in Table 2 are based on the most repeated words in the comments. The detailed representation of the given statements shows the content of the category.

Table 2. Detailed Display of the Comments Made on the Services of 5 Star Accommodation Businesses in Bodrum by Categories.

Positive Comments			Negative Comments		
Pandemic Measures	f	%	Pandemic Measures	f	%
Hygiene	364	25,31	Hygiene	60	33,71
Disinfectant	418	29,07	Disinfectant	20	11,24
Temperature Measurement	109	7,58	Temperature Measurement	13	7,30
Social Distance	100	6,95	Social Distance	68	38,20
Mask Usage	447	31,09	Mask Usage	17	9,55
Total	1438	100,00	Total	178	100,00
Room	f	%	Room	f	%
Comfort	159	22,18	Comfort	35	15,91
Width	222	30,96	Width	56	25,45
Shower/Toilet	57	7,95	Shower/Toilet	29	13,18
Cabinet	33	4,60	Cabinet	40	18,18
Sheet	246	34,31	Sheet	60	27,28
Total	717	100,00	Total	220	100,00
Price	f	%	Price	f	%
Price performance	84	80,77	Price performance	62	92,54
Extra Fees	20	19,23	Extra Fees	5	7,46
Total	104	100,00	Total	67	100,00
Staff	f	%	Staff	f	%
Smiling	2274	58,14	Rude	81	48,22
Polite	511	13,07	Interest relevance	52	30,95
Interest relevance	926	23,68	Education	35	20,83
Education	200	5,11	Total	168	100,00
Total	3911	100,00			
Cleaning	f	%	Cleaning	f	%
Room	771	62,13	Room	99	56,57
General Areas	470	37,87	General Areas	76	43,43
Total	1241	100,00	Total	175	100,00
Animation	f	%	Animation	f	%
Daytime Activities	259	33,55	Daytime Activities	65	45,77
Evening Activities	513	66,45	Evening Activities	77	54,23
Total	772	100,00	Total	142	100,00
Location	f	%	Location	f	%
Location	210	27,45	Location	5	62,50
Transportation	347	45,36	Transportation	3	37,50
environment	208	27,19	Total	8	100,00
Total	765	100,00			
Service	f	%	Service	f	%
Service	678	57,12	Service	115	38,08
Speed	509	42,88	Speed	187	61,92
Total	1187	100,00	Total	302	100,00

Table 2. Detailed Display of the Comments Made on the Services of 5 Star Accommodation Businesses in Bodrum by Categories (Continued)...

Positive Comments			Negative Comments		
Sea/Beach	f	%	Sea/Beach	f	%
Calm	73	6,85	Gizzard	95	65,52
Sand	152	14,27	Wavy	22	15,17
Large	221	20,75	Small	28	19,31
Sea	619	58,13	Total	145	100,00
Total	1065	100,00			
Customer Profile	f	%	Customer Profile	f	%
Adult	28	90,32	Noise	9	16,67
Polite	3	9,68	Rude	45	83,33
Total	31	100,00	Total	54	100,00
Children's Activities	f	%	Children's Activities	f	%
Activity	150	81,97	Activity	15	100
Trainer	33	18,03	Total	15	100,00
Total	183	100,00			
Spa/Wellness	f	%	Spa/Wellness	f	%
Massage	90	72,00	Hygiene	12	100,00
Detox	20	16,00	Total	12	100,00
Hygiene	15	12,00			
Total	125	100,00			
Security	f	%	Security	f	%
Security	131	88,51	Security	7	41,18
Measures	17	11,49	Measures	10	58,82
Total	148	100,00	Total	17	100,00
Atmosphere	f	%	Atmosphere	f	%
Nature	177	80,09	Nature	8	66,67
Ambiance	44	19,91	Ambiance	4	33,33
Total	221	100,00	Total	12	100,00
			Technical Failures		
			Air conditioning	42	60,87
			Installation	27	39,13
			Total	69	100,00
Facilities	f	%	Facilities	f	%
WIFI	28	21,7	WIFI	45	36,58
Terrace	10	7,75	TV	3	2,44
TV	5	3,88	Facilities	10	8,13
Facilities	40	31,00	Pool	20	16,26
Pool	30	23,26	Shuttle	30	24,39
Shuttle	7	5,43	Car park	15	12,20
Car park	9	6,98	Total	123	100,00
Total	129	100,00			
Sports and Playgrounds	f	%	Sports and Playgrounds	f	%
Fitness	125	59,23	Sports and Playgrounds	23	100,00
Aquapark	27	12,80	Total	23	100,00
Fun fair	22	10,43			
Sports and Playgrounds	37	17,54			
Total	211	100,00			

When customer comments are examined, it is seen that a single comment includes multiple positive and negative situations. For this reason, the main categories were divided into sub-headings and analyzed. Looking at Table 2, it is seen that 1438 positive comments were made for 5-star accommodation establishments in Bodrum in line with pandemic measures, and measures were taken in this context. Within the framework of the measures taken, it was determined that 31% of the positive comments were the use of masks, 29.07% of the use of disinfectants, 25.31% of the general hygiene rules and 6.95% of the social distance rules. In the 178 negative comments made, it is seen that pandemic measures are not taken enough. 38.20% of the negative comments are that the hotel customers and employees do not pay attention to social distance, 33.71% are deficiencies in terms of hygiene, 11.24% are not encouraged to use disinfectants, 9.55% are using masks. it is not paid attention and 7.30% of them are that there is no temperature measurement. Reviews generally show that staff follow the rules, but hotel customers do not follow the rules and there is insufficient warning.

717 of the positive customer comments are in the room category. In 34.31% of the comments, the linens are clean and of high quality, 30.96% of the comments are sufficiently wide, 22.18% are comfortable, 7.95% are new showers and toilets, and 4.60% It includes that the cabinets are sufficient. Of the 220 negative comments made about the room category, 27.28% said the rooms were narrow, 25.45% said the sheets were dirty and torn, 18.18% said the room was not comfortable, 15.91% said that there was an intense smell in the room and that the showers and toilets of 13.18% are dirty and old. While the majority of positive customer comments in the room category are about the clean sheets, most of the negative comments are about the narrowness of the rooms. It is seen that the positive and negative comments about the price are distributed close to each other. 80.77% of the 104 positive comments show that the price and performance balance is good, and 19.23% show that the extra fees are reasonable. 92.54% of the 67 negative comments made in the price category indicate that the service received is below the price, and a low rate of 7.46% is that the extra fees are unnecessary and expensive. In the price category, the majority of positive customer comments are about the price of the facility, and most of the negative comments show that the service received is not sufficient according to the price. 3911 comments made about the personnel were determined as the most positive category in general. While 58.14% of the positive comments show that the staff is friendly, 23.68% of them are in the direction of very good interest and relevance, 13.07% of them are polite and 5.11% of them are trained. It is seen that 48.22% of the 168 negative comments made are rude, 30.95% are indifferent, and 20.83% are untrained. The majority of the positive comments in the personnel category are about the friendly behavior of the personnel, while the negative comments are mostly about the rude behavior of the personnel.

It was determined that 62.13% of 1241 positive comments on cleaning were related to room cleaning and 37.87% were related to the cleaning of general areas. Of the 175 negative comments, 56.57% are in the direction of bad room cleaning, and 43.43% are in the direction of the general areas being dirty. While the most positive comments in the cleaning category are room cleaning, the majority of negative comments are related to the fact that the room cleaning is not sufficient.

While 66.45% of 772 positive comments about animation are evening activities, 33.55% are daytime activities. It was observed that customers emphasized the variety of evening activities in general, concerts and especially poolside events. It was determined that 54.23% of the 142 negative comments made were for evening activities and 45.77% for daytime activities. It was observed that the customers who made negative comments made comments that there were no evening activities and it was very quiet, and that the same activities were carried out every day regarding the daytime activities shows that.

Even if the hotel is not liked in the comments about the location, there are expressions such as the location is beautiful. 45.36% of the 765 positive comments made are

transportation, 27.45% location, 27.19% environment. The customers stated that they were pleased with the proximity of the hotel to the center of Bodrum, its location and especially the sea view, as well as the facilities such as cafes and bars in the vicinity. It is seen that 62.50% of the 8 negative comments made are related to location and 37.50% are related to transportation. While it was seen that the majority of the positive comments made in the location category were related to transportation, it was seen that the negative comments were mostly made about transportation. Customers stated that the hotel is far from the center in terms of location, and that there is no other means of transportation other than taxi.

The Service/Service category accounts for 1187 of the positive customer comments. 57.12% of the positive comments consist of very good service and 42.88% of them being fast. In the comments made, it is seen that the requests of the customers are fulfilled immediately and the service is done carefully and cleanly. Of the 302 negative comments, it was determined that 61.92% were related to speed and 38.08% were related to service. It is seen that most of the positive customer comments in the Service/Service category are due to the very good service delivery, while the negative customer comments are that queues form in the restaurants and the service slows down in line with the measures taken due to the pandemic.

In the "Food and Beverage" category, which is one of the categories that customers comment the most, 29.94% of 2298 positive comments are for dinner, 22.71% for breakfast, 18.19% for alcoholic beverages, 13.93% for snacks, Lunch is 13,05% and soft drinks are 2.18%. In the comments made, it is seen that the dinner and breakfast are quite diverse, and there are better meals from the quality restaurants outside, but it is seen that the alcoholic beverages are branded products and the fast-food products in the snack restaurant are clean and of high quality. Of the 315 negative comments, 51.43% were alcoholic beverages, 22.22% were dinner, 13.97% were breakfast, 10.79% were snacks and 1.59% were lunch. is seen. It is seen that the customer comments in the Food and Beverage category are mostly about dinner, and the most negative comments are about alcoholic beverages. There are comments from customers that they find the dinner delicious, but that alcoholic beverages are like water.

In the Sea/Beach category, 58.13% of the 1065 positive comments were distributed as the sea, 20.75% as the width of the beach, 14.27% as sand and 6.85% as calm. In the customer comments, it has been reached that the sea is one of the best in the country, the beach is wide, suitable for the hotel capacity and calm. 65.52% of the 145 negative comments made are that the beach is stony, 19.31% is small and insufficient, and 15.17% is wavy. Customers have generally commented that the beach is stony and cannot be entered without sea shoes, there is a fight for chaise lounges on the beach and they cannot find a place due to the pandemic, the sea is choppy at certain times of the day and is not suitable for children. While the positive customer comments in the Sea/Beach category are mostly about the sea, the majority of the negative comments are that the beach is stony.

Although there are not many comments on the customer profile, 90.32% of the positive issues expressed are that they are pleased to have +16 hotel customers, and 9.68% are that the customers are polite and respectful towards each other. 83.33% of the 54 negative comments made are that the customers exhibit rude behavior, and 16.67% of them are that they make too much noise in the rooms. Most of the positive customer reviews in the customer profile category are about the adult nature of the hotel, while most of the negative reviews are about the rude behavior of the customers.

It was found that 81.97% of the 183 comments in the category of children's activities were that the activities were quite diverse and sufficient, and that 18.03% of the activities were educational. It is seen that 100% of the 15 negative comments made are related to the activities, and it has been determined that the customers are of the opinion that the activities for children's activities are insufficient. Positive comments in the category of children's

activities create the diversity of the activities, while all of the negative comments indicate that the activities are inadequate.

It was determined that 72% of 125 positive comments made in the Spa/Wellness category were related to massage service, 16% were related to detox and 12% were related to hygiene. Customer comments indicate that they are quite satisfied with the massage services and that the personnel providing the service are trained in this regard. In the comments, it is seen that the word detox is used quite frequently and spa services are performed hygienically, especially during the pandemic period. 100% of the 12 negative comments are in the hygiene category. Very few of the customers say that they are not enough about hygiene and that it is not paid attention even though it is a sensitive period.

It was determined that 88.51% of the 148 positive comments made in the security category were related to security, and 11.49% were related to the measures taken. While customers expressed that they felt very safe during the pandemic period, comments were made that the lost items were found in a short time. Thanks to the security measures taken in this direction, comments were found that a safe area was created for children as well. While 58.82% of the 17 negative comments are made up of the measures taken, 41.18% is security. It was determined that a small number of customers found the security measures taken to be insufficient and that the lost items were not found again.

It was determined that 80.09% of the 221 positive comments made in the atmosphere category were related to the nature of the hotel, namely the green area, and 19.91% were related to the ambiance created by the hotel. While the nature of the hotel constitutes 66.67% of the 12 negative comments made, the ambiance is 33.33%. While the positive comments in the atmosphere category said that the hotel has grass areas and that the nature of the hotel has become different thanks to its trees and greenery, in the negative comments, the customers commented that the ambiance, lighting and building of the hotel from the first entrance were ostentatious.

The category of possibilities has an important place among the comments. Of the 129 positive comments, 31% were for the facilities, 23.26% for the pool, 21.70% for the WIFI connection, 7.75% for the terrace, 6.98% for the car park and 5.43%. Of the 123 negative comments, 36.58% are about WIFI connection, 24.39% are shuttle services, 16.26% are comments about the pool, 12.20% are parking services, 8.13 percent is amenities and 2.44% is TV. While the availability of facilities such as WIFI, terrace, TV, pool, shuttle and parking is seen as positive for the customers, it is seen that most of the customers complain about the weak internet connection. The small pool, insufficient shuttle service and insufficient capacity of the car park are other negative statements mentioned.

59.23% of the 211 positive comments made regarding sports and playgrounds are fitness, 17.54% sports and playgrounds, 12.80% aquapark and 10.43% amusement park services. Sports and playgrounds constitute 100% of the 23 negative comments. Areas such as aquaparks and amusement parks are seen to be positive by customers, and some customers state that sports and playgrounds are insufficient in general. It is seen that some customers are not satisfied with the closure of sports and playgrounds due to the pandemic. While it is seen that the most positive comments in the category of sports and playgrounds are related to fitness services, it is seen that all of the negative comments are in the direction of the lack of sports and playgrounds.

4. Conclusions, Implications and Limitations

Accommodation businesses have a great role in meeting customer needs and creating satisfaction (Arkadaş et al., 2650). The more positive experience the accommodation businesses provide to the customers, which is a promotional for the tourism industry, the more the sector will gain in that direction. At this point, it is very important to evaluate the product or service that customers experience. Consumer preferences can be affected by many possible

situations (Turunç and Yetkin, 2020). The Covid-19 pandemic has changed consumers' preferences in many positive and negative ways. For this reason, online consumer comments made to 5-star accommodation businesses during the Covid-19 period were analyzed in the study.

With the development of today's internet, customers can easily share their comments online. In this case, the more a consumer is satisfied with the product or service, the more he will benefit from the business or the destination by sharing his experiences with other people online.

According to the results of the research, it was determined that the category with the most positive comments was "personnel". These results also show that the staff is friendly. One of the biggest factors in tourists having positive or negative thoughts about the destination they go to is food and beverage services (Sormaz, 2015:49). Customers complained about the lack of variety of products and also expressed their negativity about the taste. They also stated that the food and beverage products served during the pandemic period were not hygienic enough. In line with these results, both tourism marketers and sector managers can work in line with the suggestions below. Recommendations to tourism marketers and industry managers are as follows;

- In the first category, pandemic measures, most of the positive comments are related to the use of masks, while most of the negative comments are related to social distance. In this respect, sector managers should increase their efforts to ensure customer satisfaction during the pandemic period, and ensure that customers interact with fewer people in this process by providing good training to the staff.
- While the most positive comments in the room category are clean and high quality linens, the majority of negative comments are that the rooms are narrow. In this direction, it should be included in the plans of tourism marketers to design rooms with a larger capacity while making new investments in terms of customer satisfaction.
- Most of the positive comments in the price category are that the price-performance balance is good, while the negative comments mostly complain that the service is below the price. In order to eliminate the negativity created by this situation, sector employees and managers should go to increase the service quality.
- While most of the positive comments in the personnel category indicate that the personnel is friendly, the majority of the negative comments are the rude behavior of the personnel. For this reason, in terms of ensuring customer satisfaction, it can be ensured that sector managers select qualified personnel and provide training at intervals related to communication.
- While the most positive comments in the cleaning category are about room cleaning, the majority of negative comments complain about the insufficient cleaning in the rooms. In this case, encouraging practices can be made by the sector managers for the housekeeping personnel to do their job better. In addition, work efficiency can be achieved by getting support from professionals in this field.
- While most of the positive comments in the animation category are evening activities, the majority of the negative comments are that the evening activities are inadequate and that the same shows are held constantly. In this direction, tourism marketers and sector managers can find qualified personnel for animation service and expand the organizations.
- It is seen that the positive comments made in the location category are mostly related to transportation, and most of the negative comments are related to the location of the facility. The comments made by the customers due to the location of the facility are that there are no cafes, bars and entertainment centers around the facility. For this reason, if tourism marketers and sector managers improve the cafe, bar and

entertainment services in the facilities in terms of customer satisfaction, the need for customers to go elsewhere will be eliminated.

- While the most positive comments in the Service/Service category are that the service is good, most of the negative comments are related to the speed of the service provided. It turned out that this negativity was caused by the restrictions especially during the pandemic period. In order for the process to progress better, the number of personnel should be increased according to the possibilities, and at the same time, serving the tables of the customers in order to avoid queues during the meal will result in a positive result in terms of speed.
- In the food and beverage category, most of the positive comments were about dinner, while most of the negative comments were about alcoholic beverages. In this direction, since the category that customers complain most about is food and beverage, tourism marketers and sector managers should focus more on this issue. In order for the products to be of higher quality, more budget should be allocated to this area, and especially alcoholic beverages should be presented to the customer as they are.
- In the Sea/Beach category, it was seen that the most positive comments were related to the beauty of the sea, while most of the negative comments complained that the sea was stony. What needs to be done to eliminate this negativity is to build wooden platforms on the stony areas. In this way, customers' complaints about this issue will be resolved.
- In the Customer Profile category, the most positive comments are due to the adult profile, and most of the negative comments are for rude customers. In this case, in order to ensure customer satisfaction, individuals who cause unease should be warned by the business on this issue, and at the same time, customers who create problems should be blacklisted and prevented from entering the facility. This action is necessary for other customers to have a peaceful holiday experience.
- While the majority of positive comments in the Children's Activities category are in the direction of the activities, all of the negative comments are in the direction of the limited activities. In this direction, customer satisfaction will be ensured by developing children's activities, selecting qualified personnel and employing professional child animators.
- In the Spa/Wellness category, positive comments are mostly related to massage service, while all negative comments are related to hygiene. Especially emphasizing the pandemic period, it was stated that the areas where Spa / Wellness services are provided by the customers should be more hygienic. For this reason, since these areas will contain more bacteria than other areas, attention should be paid to the hygiene of these sections. It would be appropriate for sector managers and tourism marketers to carry out disinfection practices in order to ensure the hygiene of such areas in line with their plans.
- In the security category, positive comments are mostly in the direction of security, and most of the negative comments are in line with the security measures taken. In order to eliminate this negativity, it will be possible to take these measures more by placing cameras in certain areas of the facility or by increasing the number of personnel.
- While the majority of positive comments in the atmosphere category are about the nature and green areas of the hotel, the most negative comments are that the environment in which the hotel is located is greening, the trees are not pruned and the risk of snakes is high. For this reason, it should be ensured that the trees and green areas in the enterprises are sprayed and the necessary maintenance is done.
- In the Amenities category, the most positive comments are about the facilities in the hotel, while the majority of the negative comments are about the WIFI connection. In

this direction, internet speed providers can be placed in rooms, lobbies and open areas in order to get more efficiency from the internet connection within the facility.

- While most of the positive comments in the Sports and Playgrounds category indicate that the fitness room is adequate, all of the negative comments are about sports and playgrounds in general. In this case, customers commented that the equipment in these areas is insufficient, and that there are not many sports and playgrounds in the facility. In order for the customers to spend more time in the hotel business and to be more satisfied with the service they receive, such activity areas should be expanded and the equipment should be increased.

The current study has a few limitations such as the research is limited to 5-star hotels on the Tripadvisor site. Second, within the scope of the research, comments were received between 11 March 2020 and 24 May 2021. Third, the research comments are limited to Turkish commentators only.

Taking measures against such epidemics and responding to the changing expectations of consumers will increase customer loyalty towards accommodation enterprises, and the promotion of accommodation enterprises will be facilitated by customer interaction. Future research can be done on different destinations or on different popular review sites (Trivago.com, Booking.com, Tatilsepeti.com etc.). In addition, empirical research can be developed for the effect between the answers given by the accommodation business managers and the comments of the consumers.

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